

Optimizing Characteristics of Agave Americana Fibre Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites Using Taguchi Grey Relation Analysis

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Abstract:

The present study focuses on the optimization of thermal and mechanical characteristics of Agave Americana Fibre Reinforced Composites (AAFRC) using Taguchi Grey Relational Analysis. The composite samples were manufactured through compression molding, with three factors being varied: type of polyester resin, fibre volume fraction, and composite thickness. Each factor had three levels, and a Taguchi L9 orthogonal array was employed to design the experiment, resulting in nine experimental runs. The Taguchi-GRA approach identified optimal parameters: Isophthalic Polyester Resin (Mechanical Grade), a fibre volume fraction of 0.40, and a composite thickness of 9mm. This method significantly contributed to determining the best combination of factors, enhancing the composite's overall performance. An Analysis of Variance was conducted to determine the primary influential factor, and all three factors were found to be significant. The fibre volume fraction emerged as the factor with the highest significant influence, accounting for 54.51% of the observed characteristics of manufactured composites. The tensile, flexural, impact and compressive strength of the composites exhibited a positive correlation with the fibre volume fraction, indicating the reinforcing effect of the fibres. Confirmation experiments conducted with the optimal parameters demonstrated an impressive 83.22% improvement in the grey relation grade.

Keywords: Grey Relational Analysis, Impact Strength, Leaf Fibre, Optimization Procedure, Orthogonal Array, Textile Composite, Thermoset Resin, etc.

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1 Introduction

The demand for lightweight and eco-friendly materials in various industries, including automotive, aerospace, and construction, has driven the exploration of natural fibres as an alternative to conventional synthetic reinforcements. Agave Americana, commonly known as the century plant, possesses promising mechanical properties and is abundantly available in various regions. These fibres exhibit attractive properties such as high strength, low weight, and biodegradability, making them a promising alternative to synthetic fibres in various applications. Agave Americana leaf fibre (AALF) has gained significant attention in recent years as a potential reinforcement material for composite applications [1].

The effect of fibre volume fraction, surface treatment, fibre length, type of matrix, and manufacturing process parameters on the mechanical and thermal properties of AALF-reinforced composites have been studied extensively. Several studies have explored the use of Agave Americana fibres in composite materials. Many authors investigated the mechanical properties of composites fabricated with Agave Americana fibres and found them to exhibit promising tensile strength and modulus [2], [3]. However, to fully exploit their potential, optimization of their characteristics is essential. This research focuses on optimizing the thermal and mechanical properties of Agave Americana Fibre Reinforced Composites (AAFRC) using Taguchi Grey Relational Analysis (GRA). By

systematically varying key process parameters such as fibre content, matrix type, and composite thickness, we aim to enhance the performance of AAFRC.

The application of Taguchi GRA in composite material optimization is novel and offers a systematic approach to explore multiple parameters and their levels, providing insights into the intricate relationship between process variables and composite properties. By integrating Taguchi design with GRA, this methodology allows for efficient determination of the optimal combination of parameters to maximize desired performance characteristics [4], [5].

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Material

This investigation used discontinuous Agave Americana leaf fibre as reinforcement in three thermoset polyester resin variants: Isophthalic (Mechanical Grade), Vinyl Polyester, and Unsaturated Polyester. Cobalt naphthenate and MEKP were added for faster curing. Cobalt naphthenate acts as a catalyst, promoting curing, while MEKP is a hardener, initiating crosslinking.

2.2 Fabrication of Composites

Agave Americana fibres were randomly chopped to lengths ranging from 25-50 mm before composite fabrication. Chopped AALF-reinforced composite specimens were manufactured using a compression molding machine. The specimens were prepared in a square mold made of EN90 steel, with dimensions of 350 x 350 x 10 mm. Before starting the fabrication process, the mold was coated with a release wax. Specimens were fabricated according to the design provided by the Taguchi L9 orthogonal array, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Taguchi design (for composite specimen fabrication)

Expt. No.	Coded			Uncoded		
	A	B	C	Matrix/ Resin	Composite Thickness (mm)	Fibre Volume Fraction
1	1	1	1	Isophthalic Polyester (ISO)	3	0.10
2	1	2	2	Isophthalic Polyester (ISO)	6	0.25
3	1	3	3	Isophthalic Polyester (ISO)	9	0.40
4	2	1	2	Vinyl Ester (VER)	3	0.25
5	2	2	3	Vinyl Ester (VER)	6	0.40
6	2	3	1	Vinyl Ester (VER)	9	0.10
7	3	1	3	Unsaturated Polyester (UPR)	3	0.40
8	3	2	1	Unsaturated Polyester (UPR)	6	0.10
9	3	3	2	Unsaturated Polyester (UPR)	9	0.25

A mixture of 2% Cobalt naphthenate and 3% MEKP was mixed with the resin. Reinforcing agents were impregnated with this mixture. Chopped fibres were impregnated with their respective resin and cold-pressed. These prepreps were combined until the desired fibre-resin ratio and thickness were achieved. Molds were kept under pressure for three hours. Post-curing was carried out for 24 hours at room temperature.

2.3 Characterization of Composites

Fabricated composites were evaluated for thermal and mechanical properties according to ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) standards under standard atmospheric conditions. Moisture Absorption, Thermal Conductivity, Tensile Strength and Elongation, Flexural Strength, Izod Impact Strength, and Compressive Strength of composite samples were determined according to ASTM D570, ASTM C518-04, ASTM D638, ASTM D790, ASTM D256 and ASTM D695 respectively [6].

2.4 Statistical Analysis

After testing, results (responses) were analysed by using MINITAB® statistical software and Microsoft Excel. Statistical methods like Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), regression analysis, general linear model and Taguchi, and grey relation analysis were used to analyse the data.

2.4.1 S/N Ratios in the Taguchi Method

The Signal to Noise (S/N) ratio analysis was used to evaluate the quality characteristics of AAFRC, considering two types of responses: smaller-is-better (moisture absorption and thermal conductivity) and larger-is-better (mechanical properties) [4], [7]. For the smaller-is-better responses, a lower S/N ratio, calculated using Eq. (I), indicates better performance in terms of moisture resistance and thermal insulation [8]. For mechanical properties, a higher S/N ratio, calculated using Eq. (II), indicates better performance in terms of strength and stiffness.

$$S/N_{S_{BT}} = \eta dB_{S_{BT}} = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 \right) \dots \dots (I) \quad S/N_{L_{BT}} = \eta dB_{L_{BT}} = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y_i^2} \right) \dots \dots (II)$$

Analysing S/N ratios helps determine the optimal combination of process parameters to achieve desired performance across all responses, balancing moisture resistance, thermal insulation, and mechanical strength [9].

2.4.2 Grey Relation Analysis

Optimizing multiple performance characteristics requires careful consideration compared to optimizing a single characteristic. While the Taguchi method is commonly used for single response optimization, real-world engineering applications often involve multiple response problems [10]. To effectively address these multi-response problems, it is beneficial to transform all objectives into a single equivalent objective. The integration of the Taguchi method with GRA enables the solution of such multi-response problems. GRA quantifies the absolute differences between sequences and approximates the correlation among them [11]. In this study, our goal was to minimize two performance characteristics, namely moisture absorption and thermal conductivity, while simultaneously maximizing five performance characteristics: tensile strength, elongation, flexural strength, impact strength, and compressive strength. This objective was achieved by selecting appropriate fabrication parameters, specifically the type of matrix, fibre volume fraction, and composite thickness [5], [8]. Before GRA responses for each experiment for desired composite characteristics were obtained and S/N ratios were computed.

a. Normalized S/N Ratios

The initial step is to normalize the S/N ratios, each corresponding to a specific performance characteristic to be maximized or minimized. Normalizing the objective functions allows for consistent evaluation and comparison on a standardized scale. The S/N ratio values were normalized within the range of 0 to 1 for the various responses, categorized as "smaller is better" or "larger is better" [12].

- i. **Smaller is Better:** For the responses related to moisture absorption and thermal conductivity, a lower value indicates better performance. Here, the S/N ratio min represents the minimum S/N ratio value obtained for the specific response. The S/N ratio values were normalized using Eq. (III):

$$x_{ij} = \frac{\max(y_{ij}) - y_{ij}}{\max(y_{ij}) - \min(y_{ij})} \dots \dots \dots (III) \quad x_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij} - \min(y_{ij})}{\max(y_{ij}) - \min(y_{ij})} \dots \dots \dots (IV)$$

Where x_{ij} denoted the normalized S/N Ratios (sequence) for i^{th} experiment and j^{th} response and y_{ij} represents the initial S/N Ratio of the mean of the responses [5].

- ii. **Larger is Better:** For the mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, flexural strength, and other relevant characteristics, a higher value indicates better performance. In this case, the S/N ratio max represents the maximum S/N ratio value obtained for the specific mechanical response. The S/N ratio values were normalized using Eq. (IV). The normalized S/N ratio values in the range of 0 to 1 provide a relative measure of the performance of the composite material. A value closer to zero indicates better performance for moisture absorption and thermal conductivity (Smaller is Better), while a value closer to one indicates superior performance for mechanical properties (Larger is Better) [13].

b. Deviation Sequences

After normalizing the objective functions (S/N Ratios), deviation sequences are obtained using Eq. (V). These sequences measure the deviation of each objective function from its ideal value. Deviation sequences offer insights into the contribution of each parameter level to the deviation from the ideal value for each objective function. By analysing the deviation sequences, we can identify experiments that perform exceptionally well or poorly compared

to the overall mean. This information can help in identifying the factors and levels that contribute to superior or inferior performance in terms of the various responses.

$$\Delta_{ij} = |x_{0j} - x_{ij}| \dots\dots\dots(V)$$

Where, Δ_{ij} , x_{ij} , x_{0j} refer to the deviation, comparability, and reference sequences, respectively.

c. Grey Relation Coefficient (GRC)

The grey relation coefficient (ξ) is computed by evaluating the deviation sequences for each objective function using Eq. (VI). The GRC evaluates the correlation between the deviation sequences and the ideal sequences for each objective function. It quantifies the extent of agreement between each parameter level and the ideal value associated with each objective function [14].

To determine the acceptability of the deviation, the distinguishing coefficient (ζ) of 0.5 is employed. Normalized deviations ≤ 0.5 indicate proximity to the ideal value, denoting acceptability. Deviations > 0.5 suggest a significant deviation from the ideal value, indicating undesirability. The grey relation coefficient is calculated as the average of normalized deviations for each parameter setting. A higher grey relation coefficient indicates a stronger correlation with the desired performance.

$$\xi(x_{0j}, x_{ij}) = \frac{(\Delta_{min} + \zeta \Delta_{max})}{(\Delta_{ij} + \zeta \Delta_{max})} \dots\dots\dots(VI)$$

In the given context, $\xi(x_{0j}, x_{ij})$ represents the GRC of individual response variables, which is calculated based on the minimum deviation (Δ_{min}) and maximum deviation (Δ_{max}) values associated with each response variable [5], [13].

d. Grey Relation Grade (GRG) and Rank

The Grey Relation Grad denoted as Y_i assesses the overall performance of each parameter level relative to the ideal values across all objectives. It quantifies the correlation between parameter levels and desired objectives in multi-objective optimization. The GRG is computed by averaging the Grey Relational Coefficients obtained for all responses (Eq. (VII)) [15].

$$Y_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \xi_i(j) \dots\dots\dots(VII)$$

In this context, Y_i represents the GRG value computed for the i^{th} experiment, with n denoting the number of performance characteristics targeted for optimization. On the other hand, ξ_i refers to the grey relation coefficient associated with the i^{th} experiment.

The parameter levels are ranked based on the GRG values. The rank reflects the relative effectiveness of each parameter level in achieving the desired objectives. Levels with higher GRG values are considered more optimal for multi-objective optimization [5], [13], [16].

e. Selection of Optimal Levels of Process Parameters

The selection of optimal levels for process parameters is based on the rankings obtained in the previous step. The levels associated with higher rankings are chosen as the optimal configuration for multi-objective optimization. These levels effectively balance various performance characteristics, resulting in overall improvement.

f. Prediction and Validation

Once the optimal level of composite manufacturing has been identified, the subsequent step entails predicting and verifying the improvement in performance characteristics using the selected composite manufacturing parameters. The predicted grey relational grade denoted as y_{pred} , can be calculated using Eq. (VIII) [4], [13].

$$y_{pred} = y_{expt} + \sum_{j=1}^k (y_j - y_{expt}) \dots\dots\dots(VIII)$$

Where, y_{pred} represents the predicted value, y_{expt} is the overall mean response (GRG) for the entire orthogonal array, y_j is the mean response (GRG) for the factor at the optimum level, and k denotes the number of main factors affecting the response [4], [17].

3 Results and Discussion

After manufacturing the Agave Americana fibre reinforced composites according to Taguchi L9 orthogonal array, all the samples were characterized for thermal and mechanical characteristics. Table 2 represents the properties of AAFRC for every experiment.

Table 2 Properties of Agave Americana Fibre Reinforced Composites

Expt. No.	Coded Factors			Responses						
	A	B	C	Moisture Absorption (%)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (J/m ²)	Compressive Strength (MPa)
1	1	1	1	0.7	0.08417	31.01	4.06	17.74	30.8	5.41
2	1	2	2	2.34	0.04839	96.08	3.61	67.26	125.98	17.65
3	1	3	3	5.99	0.03578	173.98	3.03	115.41	216.45	33.03
4	2	1	2	3.12	0.06828	31.17	3.12	20.56	31.98	6.11
5	2	2	3	5.92	0.10511	110.94	2.32	72.97	129.06	20.82
6	2	3	1	5.16	0.04176	62.73	3.12	43.91	60.47	14.05
7	3	1	3	6.69	0.11916	53.92	1.98	35.81	48.7	11.19
8	3	2	1	5.31	0.07514	30.98	2.34	21.06	25.71	6.60
9	3	3	2	9.12	0.02542	97.06	1.94	64.66	114.15	17.59

The ANOVA results are presented in Table 3. ANOVA analysis reveals that matrix type, composite thickness, and fibre volume fraction significantly affect most AAFRC properties. Contribution (%) written in bracket gives the information about the degree of changes brought by a specific factor to the tested property of composite. Composite thickness has the most significant impact, while matrix type is insignificant for thermal conductivity and fibre volume fraction is insignificant for elongation. These findings offer scientific guidance for optimizing the manufacturing parameters of these composites to achieve desired performance characteristics based on the specific property of interest.

Table 3 Factor-wise p-Values and Contribution (%)

Property	Matrix	Composite Thickness (mm)	Fibre Volume Fraction
Moisture Absorption (%)	0.019 (48.26%)	0.027 (32.68%)	0.048 (18.14%)
Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	0.312 (6.56%)	0.045 (62.27%)	0.095 (28.2%)
Tensile Strength (MPa)	0.049 (14.48%)	0.017 (43.15%)	0.018 (41.62%)
Elongation (%)	0.008 (75.67%)	0.104 (5.04%)	0.03 (18.71%)
Flexural Strength (MPa)	0.016 (13.99%)	0.005 (45.54%)	0.006 (40.23%)
Impact Strength (J/m ²)	0.049 (19.66%)	0.025 (40.19%)	0.025 (39.12%)
Compressive Strength (MPa)	0.018 (12.16%)	0.005 (46.72%)	0.005 (40.89%)

3.1 Grey Relation Analysis

3.1.1 S/N Ratios

For moisture absorption and thermal conductivity, a smaller S/N ratio is preferred (smaller is better). Conversely, for mechanical properties, a larger S/N ratio is desired (larger is better). S/N ratios calculated for each response are shown in Table 4.

Experiments three consistently exhibit higher S/N ratios, indicating superior performance across multiple characteristics, while experiments 1 and 9 consistently have lower S/N ratios, suggesting poorer performance. These findings can guide the optimization of the manufacturing process to enhance the desired characteristics, considering the influence of the factors studied in the experiment [18]. Since multi-objective optimization is to be performed,

these S/N ratios need to be normalized on a scale of 0 to 1. Using Eq. (III) and Eq. (IV), normalized S/N ratios were obtained for all the responses and reported in

Table 5.

3.1.2 Normalized S/N Ratios

The normalization of values enables a comparative evaluation of the factors and their influence on the responses. The experiments with lower values for moisture absorption and thermal conductivity are desirable. From the data, we can see that experiment one has the lowest normalized value for moisture absorption, indicating better moisture resistance. Experiment nine has the lowest normalized value for thermal conductivity, suggesting lower heat transfer characteristics.

Table 4 Signal to Noise Ratios

Expt. No.	Coded Factors			S/N Ratios						
	A	B	C	Moisture Absorption (%)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (J/m ²)	Compressive Strength (MPa)
1	1	1	1	3.10	21.50	29.83	12.17	24.98	29.77	14.66
2	1	2	2	-7.38	26.30	39.65	11.15	36.56	42.01	24.93
3	1	3	3	-15.55	28.93	44.81	9.63	41.24	46.71	30.38
4	2	1	2	-9.88	23.31	29.87	9.88	26.26	30.10	15.72
5	2	2	3	-15.45	19.57	40.90	7.31	37.26	42.22	26.37
6	2	3	1	-14.25	27.58	35.95	9.88	32.85	35.63	22.95
7	3	1	3	-16.51	18.48	34.64	5.93	31.08	33.75	20.98
8	3	2	1	-14.50	22.48	29.82	7.38	26.47	28.20	16.39
9	3	3	2	-19.20	31.90	39.74	5.76	36.21	41.15	24.91

Table 5 Normalized Signal to Noise Ratios

Expt. No.	Coded Factors			Normalized Signal to Noise Ratios						
	A	B	C	Moisture Absorption (%) *	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK) *	Tensile Strength (MPa) #	Elongation (%) #	Flexural Strength (MPa) #	Impact Strength (J/m ²) #	Compressive Strength (MPa) #
1	1	1	1	0	0.7750	0.0006	1	0	0.0848	0
2	1	2	2	0.4701	0.4167	0.6559	0.8409	0.7117	0.7460	0.6536
3	1	3	3	0.8362	0.2213	1	0.6038	1	1	1
4	2	1	2	0.5822	0.6396	0.0035	0.6434	0.0788	0.1024	0.0673
5	2	2	3	0.8317	0.9188	0.7393	0.2422	0.7552	0.7573	0.7449
6	2	3	1	0.7781	0.3213	0.4088	0.6434	0.4840	0.4014	0.5275
7	3	1	3	0.8793	1	0.3211	0.0276	0.3751	0.2998	0.4017
8	3	2	1	0.7893	0.7015	0	0.2538	0.0916	0	0.1099
9	3	3	2	1	0	0.6618	0	0.6906	0.6997	0.6517

Experiment three has the highest normalized value exhibiting the highest values for most of the mechanical properties, indicating better overall performance. It suggests that the factors corresponding to experiment 3 may contribute positively to achieving the desired mechanical characteristics in the AAFRC.

3.1.3 Deviation Sequences

The deviation sequences represent the deviation of each response value from the overall mean for that particular response. It allows us to understand the relative performance of each experiment compared to the mean. Computed

deviation sequences are given in Experiment three with lower deviation sequences to most of the characteristics contributes to superiority in terms of the various responses to achieve the desired optimization objectives.

Grey Relation Coefficient and Grey Relation Grade

Based on the provided grey relation coefficient, grey relation grade and rank table (Table 7), we can draw several findings regarding the performance of the experiments. The grey relation coefficient represents the closeness or similarity of each experiment to the ideal solution, while the grey relation grade provides a comprehensive ranking of the experiments based on their performance.

Table 6. Experiment three with lower deviation sequences to most of the characteristics contributes to superiority in terms of the various responses to achieve the desired optimization objectives.

3.1.4 Grey Relation Coefficient and Grey Relation Grade

Based on the provided grey relation coefficient, grey relation grade and rank table (Table 7), we can draw several findings regarding the performance of the experiments. The grey relation coefficient represents the closeness or similarity of each experiment to the ideal solution, while the grey relation grade provides a comprehensive ranking of the experiments based on their performance.

Table 6 Deviation Sequences

Expt. No.	Coded Factors			Deviation Sequences						
	A	B	C	Moisture Absorption (%)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (J/m ²)	Compressive Strength (MPa)
1	1	1	1	1	0.2250	0.9994	0	1	0.9152	1
2	1	2	2	0.5299	0.5833	0.3441	0.1591	0.2883	0.2540	0.3464
3	1	3	3	0.1638	0.7787	0	0.3962	0	0	0
4	2	1	2	0.4178	0.3604	0.9965	0.3566	0.9212	0.8976	0.9327
5	2	2	3	0.1683	0.0812	0.2607	0.7578	0.2448	0.2427	0.2551
6	2	3	1	0.2219	0.6787	0.5912	0.3566	0.5160	0.5986	0.4725
7	3	1	3	0.1207	0	0.6789	0.9724	0.6249	0.7002	0.5983
8	3	2	1	0.2107	0.2985	1	0.7462	0.9084	1	0.8901
9	3	3	2	0	1	0.3382	1	0.3094	0.3003	0.3483

Based on the grey relation grade, experiment 3 (A1B3C3) has the highest grade, indicating its overall best performance across all the considered factors. Experiment five follows with the second-highest grade, suggesting its strong overall performance. Experiments can be ranked based on their grey relation ranks. Experiment 3 (A1B3C3) holds the first rank, indicating its superior overall performance. Experiment 5 (A2B2C3) secures the second rank, followed by experiment 2 (A1B2C3) in the third rank.

Table 7 GRC, GRG and Rank

Expt. No.	Coded Factors			Grey Relational Coefficient							GRG	Rank
	A	B	C	Moisture Absorption (%)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (J/m ²)	Compressive Strength (MPa)		
1	1	1	1	0.3333	0.6896	0.3335	1	0.3333	0.3533	0.3333	0.4823	7
2	1	2	2	0.4855	0.4615	0.5924	0.7586	0.6343	0.6631	0.5907	0.5980	3
3	1	3	3	0.7533	0.3910	1	0.5579	1	1	1	0.8146	1
4	2	1	2	0.5448	0.5811	0.3341	0.5837	0.3518	0.3578	0.3490	0.4432	9

5	2	2	3	0.7481	0.8603	0.6572	0.3975	0.6713	0.6732	0.6622	0.6671	2
6	2	3	1	0.6927	0.4242	0.4582	0.5837	0.4921	0.4551	0.5141	0.5172	6
7	3	1	3	0.8055	1	0.4241	0.3396	0.4445	0.4166	0.4553	0.5551	5
8	3	2	1	0.7035	0.6262	0.3333	0.4012	0.3550	0.3333	0.3597	0.4446	8
9	3	3	2	1	0.3333	0.5965	0.3333	0.6178	0.6247	0.5894	0.5850	4

Based on the grey relation coefficients, grades, and ranks, experiment 3 (A1B3C3) demonstrates the best overall performance, while experiment 4 (A2B1C2) shows a weaker performance. Experiments 5, 2, 9, and 7 also display favourable performance in various aspects. These findings provide valuable insights into the relative performance of the experiments and can assist in identifying the most promising solutions or factors contributing to optimal results.

3.1.5 Selection of Optimal Levels

From the grey relation grade, it is evident that experiment three gives the most desired composite characteristics. The obtained grey relation grades were further analysed to validate the prediction and determine the exact experimental setup that gives optimal setup. The main Effects Plot for Means and S/N Ratios of Grey Relation Grade are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Main Effects Plot for Means and S/N Ratios of Grey Relation Grade

Higher grey relation grade and S/N ratio indicate the levels that contribute to superior performance in terms of the various responses. Here, composite samples manufactured with Isophthalic Polyester Resin with 9 mm composite thickness, and 0.4 fibre volume fraction exhibit higher GRG and S/N ratio. This setup corresponds to experiment 3 (A1B3C3). Hence the parameters set in experiment 3 (A1B3C3) will be treated as optimal parameters.

Table 8 represents the level-wise mean response table for the grey relation grade. Higher GRG was obtained for level 3 of the factors composite thickness (mm) and fibre volume fraction whereas higher GRG was obtained for level 1 of Matrix indicating A1B3C3 as an optimal setting. When it comes to rank, fibre volume fraction shows a higher rank indicating a significant influence of the composite characteristics.

Table 8 Response Table for Grey Relational Grade

Factor	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Max-Min	Rank
Matrix (A)	0.631653	0.528241	0.542592	0.103412	3
Composite Thickness (B)	0.493536	0.569921	0.638329	0.144793	2
Fibre Volume Fraction (C)	0.481378	0.54207	0.678938	0.19756	1

To evaluate the significance and percentage contribution of each factor to the multiple characteristics of AALF reinforced composites, an ANOVA analysis was performed on the GRG at a confidence level of 95%. The outcomes of this analysis, demonstrating the relative effects of the factors, are presented in Table 9 [16].

Table 9 ANOVA of Grey Relation Grade

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Matrix	2	0.018847	16.72%	0.018847	0.009423	27.43	0.035
Composite Thickness (mm)	2	0.031736	28.16%	0.031736	0.015868	46.18	0.021
Fibre Volume Fraction	2	0.061446	54.51%	0.061446	0.030723	89.42	0.011
Error	2	0.000687	0.61%	0.000687	0.000344		
Total	8	0.112716	100.00%				

R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
99.39%	97.56%	87.65%

According to the analysis, the fibre volume fraction demonstrates the highest influence, accounting for 54.51% of the variation in the GRG. Following that, the composite thickness contributes 28.16%, while the matrix exhibits a minimal influence of 16.72%. Additionally, the p-values of all factors being less than 0.05 signify their significant impacts on the composite characteristics. The high R values indicate a good fit for the developed model. These findings provide valuable insights into the importance of each factor and contribute to optimizing the manufacturing parameters of AALF reinforced composites for enhanced performance.

3.2 Prediction and Validation

The predicted grey relation grade was computed using Eq. (VIII). Confirmation tests were carried out to validate the results of the analysis, and the average GRG was calculated based on nine experimental runs [16]. Before the optimization study, the composites were manufactured with the setting A3B2C1 and the optimized setting as per the GRA is A1B3C3. Table 10 demonstrates that the results from the confirmation experiment align well with the predicted values. Furthermore, an impressive 83.22% improvement in GRG was observed. This enhancement in experimental results validates the effectiveness of utilizing the Taguchi method in conjunction with GRA to enhance the characteristics of AAFRC. The predictions and results validation were based on the mean response of the GRG values for each experiment, as indicated in Eq. (VIII) [5].

Table 10 Composite Characteristics Using Initial and Optimal Setting

Properties	Initial Factors	Optimal Factors	
		Prediction	Experiment
Levels	A3B2C1	A1B3C3	A1B3C3
Moisture Absorption (%)	5.31		5.99
Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	0.07514		0.03578
Tensile Strength (MPa)	30.98		173.98
Elongation (%)	2.34		3.03
Flexural Strength (MPa)	21.06		115.41
Impact Strength (J/m ²)	25.71		216.45
Compressive Strength (MPa)	6.60		33.03
Grey Relation Grade	0.4446	0.814107111	0.8146

4 Conclusion

Resin type, composite thickness, and fibre volume fraction significantly impact composite performance, with fibre volume fraction exerting the strongest influence, followed by composite thickness. The optimized parameter settings for desired characteristics entail employing Isophthalic Polyester Resin, a 9 mm thickness, and a 0.4 fibre volume fraction (experiment 3). The alignment between predicted GRG values and confirmation experiments validates the efficacy of Taguchi GRA. Confirmation tests demonstrate an impressive 83.22% improvement in GRG, providing strong evidence of the successful optimization of Agave Americana Fibre Reinforced Composites. These findings yield valuable insights into the influence of factors on thermal and mechanical characteristics, offering robust

scientific guidance for optimizing the manufacturing parameters and attaining the desired performance in different application areas.

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